

α -Glucosidase inhibition and DPPH free radical scavenging by oxovanadium(IV) complexes of some tetradentate Schiff bases[†]

Sristicheta Misra^a, Krishna Bihari Pandeya^{a*}, Ashok Kumar Tiwari^{b*}, Amtul Zehra Ali^b and T. Saradamani^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : kbpandeya@yahoo.com

^bDivision of Pharmacology, Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad-500 007, India

Manuscript received 04 July 2011, accepted 05 July 2011

Abstract : α -Glucosidase inhibition and DPPH free radical scavenging by four oxovanadium(IV) complexes of tetradentate Schiff bases, derived from salicylaldehyde/5-bromosalicylaldehyde and ethylenediamine/phenylenediamine (VO-salen, VO-brsalen, VO-salphn and VO-brsalphn), have been screened. Among the four complexes studied, VO-salen shows best α -glucosidase inhibition and also best DPPH free radical scavenging property.

Keywords : α -Glucosidase inhibition, DPPH free radical scavenging, vanadyl complexes, VO(salen).

1. Introduction

Glucosidase inhibitors have been found useful in reducing postprandial hyperglycemic excursion both in Type-I and Type-II diabetes and have proved to be drugs of choice for first line treatment¹⁻⁴. Similarly antioxidants that scavenge free radicals possess preventive as well as therapeutic potentials⁵⁻¹¹ against free radical mediated diseases, including diabetes. Researches on α -glucosidase inhibitors and DPPH free radical scavengers have, therefore, been actively pursued with the aim to develop therapeutics for the treatment of diabetes and other carbohydrate and free radical mediated diseases^{12,13}. Most of the work in this area has, however, been centered on the organic molecules both natural and synthetic¹⁴⁻²⁴.

Oxovanadium(IV) complexes of a variety of organic ligands are known to show antidiabetic properties²⁵⁻³⁴. Insulin-like effects of VO-salen complex on carbohydrate metabolism has earlier been studied by Durai and Saminathan³⁵ to find that the blood glucose levels of rats with alloxan induced diabetes dropped from hyperglycemic levels to hypoglycemic levels after treatment for a period of 30 days. The optimum dose of the reagent to produce the normoglycemic levels in the diabetic rats

was 7.5 mg of vanadium per kg body weight per day. The complex activates the glycolysis, glycogenesis and depresses the glycogenolysis and gluconeogenesis in the diabetic rats, suggesting its insulin-like nature. However, α -glucosidase inhibition screening of such oxovanadium(IV) complexes has received comparatively much less attention^{36,37}. In the present paper we report α -glucosidase inhibition and DPPH free radical scavenging measurements on VO-salen and three other oxovanadium(IV) complexes (Fig. 1) of structurally related Schiff base ligands.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of the complexes :

The complexes were prepared by simple reaction of vanadyl sulphate and the ligands in equimolar ratio in methanol. All the complexes show satisfactory elemental analyses (Table 1) and characteristic strong symmetric infrared bands for $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ (Table 1). The electronic spectra of the complexes exhibit bands corresponding to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$ (ν_3) for oxovanadium(IV) complexes (Table 1).

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

X = H VO-salen (1)
X = Br VO-brsalen (2)

X = H VO-salphn (3)
X = Br VO-brsalphn (4)

Fig. 1. Structures of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes.

in Table 2. A perusal of the formal redox potential (E^0) data for the four complexes reveals that VO-salpn and VO-brsalen both show more positive E^0 values than that of VO-salen; the increase being higher for VO-salpn than for VO-brsalen. More +ve E^0 value indicates smaller electron density on the metal centre and vice-versa. The above observation is in line with the electron withdrawing properties of bromide present on the salicylaldehyde moiety in VO-brsalen and of the phenylene backbone present in VO-salpn. It has earlier been established^{38,39} that the presence of electron withdrawing groups, aromatic rings and/or double bonds in the equatorial ligands decreases the electron density on central metal ion and facilitates its reduction. These observations also tally with the EPR parameters of the two complexes⁴⁰. Anisotropy in the g -value ($g_{\perp} - g_{\parallel}$) that gives a measure of the in-plane ligand field strength is smaller for VO-salpn (0.021) than for VO-salen (0.032) suggesting larger in-plane ligand field strength for VO-salen. In the E^0 value of VO-brsalphn, addition of the effect of the bromide group and

Table 1. Elemental analyses and IR and electronic spectra

Complex	Elemental analyses (%) :			IR band (cm^{-1})	Electronic spectra		
	Calcd./ (Found)				$\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$	ν_1 (cm^{-1})	ν_2 (cm^{-1})
VO-salen	C	H	N	970	12500	16700	Not resolved
	57.67 (57.08)	4.20 (4.29)	8.41 (8.82)				
VO-brsalen	C	H	N	962	12800	17250	25000
	39.10 (39.30)	2.44 (2.33)	5.70 (5.88)				
VO-salphn	C	H	N	983	12500	16700	Not resolved
	62.99 (63.31)	3.67 (3.69)	7.35 (7.38)				
VO-brsalphn	C	H	N	969	12200	16130	25000
	44.53 (44.31)	2.23 (2.29)	5.19 (5.10)				

2.2. Cyclic voltammetry :

Cyclic voltammetry was carried out with a Bioanalytical System (BAS-100) electrochemical analyzer. The cell was a standard three electrode system with a platinum wire auxiliary as the counter electrode. The measurements were performed at room temperature in DMSO containing 0.1 M TBAP. The solution was deoxygenated by purging nitrogen gas.

All the complexes show simple quasi-reversible wave for $\text{VO}^{2+/3+}$ redox couple in +1000 to 0 mV potential range. A representative voltammogram has been presented in Fig. 2 and values of various CV parameters are given

that of the phenylene group is reflected. Adding the two effects to the E^0 value of VO-salen, an estimate of the E^0 value for VO-brsalphn comes out to be 617 mV, close to the experimental value (650 mV); the small difference accounts the steric effects³⁹.

2.3. α -Glucosidase inhibition :

Rat intestinal acetone powder (Sigma chemicals, USA) was sonicated properly in normal saline (100 : 1 w/v) and after centrifugation at 3000 rpm \times 30 mins the supernatant was treated as crude intestinal α -glucosidase. Ten microliters of test samples dissolved in DMSO (5 mg/ml solution) were mixed and incubated with 50 μ l of enzyme in a 96-well microplate for 5 mins. Reaction mixture was

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of VO-salen (3 mM in DMSO), supporting electrolyte 0.1 M TBAP, scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹

Table 2. CV parameters

Complex	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E^0 (mV)	I_{pc} (mA)	I_{pa} (mA)	I_{pc}/I_{pa}
VO-salen	379	466	422	3.78	4.81	0.79
VO-salphen	499	588	543	3.02	2.74	1.10
VO-brsalen	448	544	496	3.42	2.65	1.29
VO-brsalphen	609	692	650	3.56	4.22	0.84

further incubated for another 10 mins with 50 μ l substrate (5 mM, *p*-nitrophenyl- α -D-glucopyranoside) prepared in 100 mM phosphate buffer (pH ~ 6.8) and release of nitrophenol was read at, 405 nm spectrophotometrically (SPECTRA_{max} PLUS³⁸⁴, Molecular devices, USA). Percent α -glucosidase inhibition was calculated as $(1-B/A) \times 100$, where A was the absorbance of reactants without test samples and B was absorbance of reactants with test samples. All the samples were run in triplicate and acarbose was taken as standard reference compound. Several dilutions of primary solution (5 mg/ml DMSO) were made and assayed accordingly to obtain concentration of the test sample required to inhibit 50% activity (IC_{50}) of the enzyme applying suitable regression analysis.

Results of α -glucosidase inhibition experiments with the four complexes are presented in Fig. 3. The IC_{50} values for the four complexes follow the order : VO-salen (7.7 μ M) < VO-brsalen (20.5 μ M) \approx VO-brsalphen (23 μ M) < VO-salphen (34 μ M).

2.3.1. VO-salen vs VO-salphen :

VO-salen shows stronger α -glucosidase inhibition than VO-salphen; IC_{50} values being 7.7 μ M and 34 μ M respectively. Cyclic voltammetric studies on the two complexes yield formal redox potential (E^0) values of 422 mV (VO-salen) and 543 mV (VO-salphen), indicating higher electron density on the central metal ion in VO-salen than in VO-salphen. These observations suggest that higher electron density on vanadium favours the inhibitory potential of the oxovanadium(IV) complex. Ashiq *et al.* have also arrived at similar conclusion in their α -glucosidase inhibition studies on oxovanadium(IV) complexes of hydrazide ligands³⁶.

Inhibition of α -glucosidase by any inhibitor requires some kind of interaction between the enzyme and the inhibitor. Cornman *et al.* have suggested that binding of

Fig. 3. α -Glucosidase inhibitory activity of VO-complexes. Inhibitory concentration required to inhibit 50% activity of the enzyme ($IC_{50\%}$) were calculated by applying logarithmic regression analysis. It was 7.7 μ M for VO-salen, 20.5 μ M for VO-brsalen, 23 μ M for VO-brsalphn and 34 μ M for complex VO-salphn. Values represent mean \pm standard deviation, $n = 3$.

protein (side chains) to the metal ion causes inhibition or activation of the enzymes⁴¹. Based on the observation that free hydrazide ligands do not show any inhibition of α -glucosidase, while their oxovanadium(IV) complexes show varying degree of inhibitory activity. Ashiq *et al.* have concluded the essential role of the metal center in the inhibitory potential of the oxovanadium(IV) complexes. In a recent computational study Zhou *et al.*⁴² demonstrated that capability of the inhibitor to form hydrogen bond(s) with the catalytic residue(s) of the enzyme is important in the inhibition of the glucosidase activity. Even more recently Park *et al.*⁴³ have also used computational approach to interpret the relative inhibitory potentials of acarbose and four newly identified α -glucosidase inhibitors, whose activities are quite close to that of acarbose. They have concluded that the inhibitors can be stabilized in the active site of the enzyme through the formation of multiple hydrogen bonds with catalytic residues and through the establishment of hydrophobic contacts in a cooperative fashion.

Such interactions between α -glucosidase and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of the present study may occur through

binding of protein side chain(s) to the sixth position (trans to the vanadyl oxygen) in the complex and through hydrophobic or H-bonding interactions of enzyme side chains with the coordinated Schiff base ligands. Binding of a ternary ligand to VO(salen) has been studied^{44,45} amply and proven experimentally as shown in Fig. 4. Park *et al.*⁴³ have also shown that in formation of hydrogen-bonds between the inhibitor and the α -glucosidase, some of the protein side-chains act as hydrogen-bond acceptors (e.g. Thr 215 and Glu 276) and some others act as hydrogen-bond donors (e.g. Ser 244). Obviously appropriate functional groups available on the inhibitor molecule act as hydrogen-bond donors and hydrogen-bond acceptors, respectively. For the inhibitors, under discussion, the two phenoxy groups available on the coordinated Schiff base ligands are the apparent hydrogen-bond acceptors.

'Metal to protein (side chain) bond model' does not fully account for the observation that higher electron density on the metal atom favors higher inhibition, because higher electron density on the central metal ion should lead to weaker metal-protein (side chain) bond, hence weaker enzyme inhibition. Hydrophobic or H-bonding

Fig. 4. Equilibrium of binding a ternary ligand X to $[V^{IV}O(\text{salen})]$.

interactions of protein side chains with the coordinated Schiff base ligand, thus, appear to have more important role to play in the mechanism of inhibition of α -glucosidase by the oxovanadium(IV) complexes. At this point it may be noted that all the four ligands of our study show inhibition of α -glucosidase even in free (uncoordinated) state (% inhibition at 200 μM inhibitor concentration : salen 29.4, salphn 57.9, brsalen 14.4, brsalphn 58.8), while none of the hydrazide ligands of Ashiq *et al.* show any inhibition in free (uncoordinated) state³⁶.

It is also important to note that in free state salphn is a stronger inhibitor of α -glucosidase in comparison to salen suggesting that the hydrophobic or H-bonding interactions between the Schiff base and the protein side-chains are stronger in case of salphn than in salen. Presence of electron withdrawing phenylene backbone in place of simple ethylene backbone seems to be the obvious reason. On complex formation, however, VO-salen becomes much stronger an α -glucosidase inhibitor than VO-salphn. Apparently, on complex formation, hydrophobic or H-bonding ability of the Schiff base with the protein side chain is enhanced to much greater extent in the case of salen than in salphn.

2.3.2. VO-brsalen vs VO-brsalphn :

Similar comparison between VO-brsalen and VO-brsalphn reveals that the effect of aromatic group phenylene replacing the simple ethylene group, as the backbone is not as pronounced as in VO-salen vs VO-salphn comparison. VO-brsalen shows only slightly higher inhibition potential; the two inhibitors having IC_{50} values of : VO-brsalen, 20.5 μM and VO-brsalphn 23 μM . Presence of bromide on the salicylaldehyde moiety in the ligand molecule thus mars the ethylene vs phenylene effect on the inhibition potential.

2.3.3. VO-salen vs VO-brsalen and VO-salphn vs VO-brsalphn :

In comparison to VO-salen, VO-brsalen shows higher inhibition at higher concentrations and lower inhibition at lower concentrations; profile curves for the two complexes crossing each other at 50 μM (Fig. 3). Similarly, compared to VO-salphn, VO-brsalphn shows higher inhibition at high concentrations and lower inhibition at lower concentration; the two profile curves crossing each other at 21 μM . These observations suggest that the mode of interaction of VO-brsalen and VO-brsalphn with α -glucosidase is not same as that of VO-salen and VO-salphn. It is apparent that the Br groups available on the coordinated Schiff base ligands in VO-brsalen and VO-brsalphn may act as hydrogen-bond acceptors to form additional hydrogen-bonds with suitable hydrogen-bond donor side chain on the enzyme.

2.4. DPPH free radical scavenging :

DPPH free radical scavenging activity was tested with 25 μl of test sample (1 mg/mL DMSO), 125 μl of 0.1 M Tris- HCl buffer (pH \sim 7.4) and 125 μl of 0.5 mM DPPH (1,1-diphenyl-2-picrylhydrazyl; Sigma chemicals, USA, dissolved in absolute ethyl alcohol) were mixed and shaken well. After incubating 20 mins in dark, absorbance was recorded spectrophotometrically (SPECTRA_{max} PLUS³⁸⁴, Molecular devices, USA) at 517 nm. The free radical scavenging potential was determined as the percent decolourisation of DPPH due to the test samples and calculated as $(1 - B/A) \times 100$, where A is absorbance of DPPH control with solvent, and B is absorbance of decolourized DPPH in the presence of test compound. All the analysis was done in duplicate; trolox was taken as reference compound. Several dilutions of primary solution (1 mg/ml DMSO) were made and assayed accordingly to obtain concentration of the sample required to

Fig. 5. DPPH scavenging activity of VO-salen and VO-salphn

scavenge 50% (SC_{50}) of DPPH free radical applying suitable regression analysis.

All the four complexes have also been screened for their DPPH free radical scavenging property. At 250 μ M concentration the percentage DPPH free radical scavenging by the four complexes is : VO-salen, 76.3, VO-salphn, 63.1, VO-brsalen, 41.3 and VO-brsalphn 0.0.

Only two of the complexes (VO-salen and VO-salphn) show more than 60% DPPH free radical scavenging at 250 μ M and have been chosen for SC_{50} % (μ M) determination. The experimental results are shown in Fig. 5, which yields the SC_{50} % (μ M) values as : VO-salen, 57.16 and VO-salphn, 113.25.

2.4.1. Comparison with free (uncoordinated) ligands :

It may be noted here that only two of the ligands (salphn and brsalphn) used in the present study show DPPH free radical scavenging activity at the experimental concentration (250 μ M). Salphn scavenges DPPH free radical to the extent of 75.3% and brsalphn to the extent of 25.6%; SC_{50} value for salphn being 115.4 μ M. The observation that salphn and brsalphn scavenge the DPPH free radical but salen and brsalen do not show any scavenging at 250 μ M suggests the role of the phenylene backbone in the DPPH free radical scavenging property of the free (uncoordinated) ligand. On complex formation with oxovanadium(IV), the scavenging potentials of

both salphn and brsalphn decreases and those of both salen and brsalen get increased.

Results of our experiments suggest that among the four complexes studied, VO-salen is the best α -glucosidase inhibitor and also best DPPH free radical scavenger.

Acknowledgements

This work has been done with financial assistance from University Grants Commission, New Delhi (F.No. 31-109/2005(SR)). Authors are thankful to Dr. R. N. Patel of A. P. S. University, Rewa for providing facility for cyclic voltammetric measurements and to Dr. J. S. Yadav, the Director, Indian Institute of Chemical Technology, Hyderabad for providing necessary facilities for biological activity screening and evaluation of the compounds.

References

- 1 K C Maki, M L Carson, M P Miller, M Turowski, M Bell, D M Wildor and M S Reeves, *Diabetes Care*, 2007, **30**, 1039
- 2 K S Lam, S C Tiu, M W Tsang T P Ip and S C Tam, *Diabetes Care*, 1998, **21**, 1154
- 3 S A Raptis and G D Dimitriadis, *Exp Clin Endocrinol Diabetes*, 2001, **109**, 265
- 4 G Dimitriadis, E Hatziaellaki, E Alexopoulos, O Kordonouri, V Komesidou, M Ganotakis and S Raptis, *Diabetes Care*, 1991, **14**, 393

5. B. Halliwell, *Lancet*, 1994, **344**, 721.
6. C. Noguchi and E. Nikki, *Biol. Med.*, 2000, **28**, 1538.
7. K. N. Prasad, W. C. Cole, A. R. Hovland, K. C. Prasad, B. K. Nahreini, J. Edward-Prasad and C. P. Andreatta, *Curr. Opin. Neurol.*, 1999, **12**, 761.
8. A. K. Tiwari, *J. Med. Arom. Plant Sci.*, 1999, **21**, 230.
9. F. Visioli, L. Borsani and C. Galli, *Cardiovas. Res.*, 2000, **47**, 419.
10. F. Visioli, J. F. Kearey and B. Halliwell, *Cardiovas. Res.*, 2000, **47**, 409.
11. P. G. Winyard and D. R. Blake, *Adv. Pharmacol.*, 1997, **38**, 4403.
12. K. C. Maki, *Am. J. Cardiol.*, 2004, 9312C-17C.
13. S. Delorme and J. L. Chiasson, *Curr. Opin. Pharmacol.*, 2005, **5**, 184.
14. E. B. De Melo, A. S. Gomes and I. Carvalho, *Tetrahedron*, 2006, **62**, 10277.
15. T. H. Babu, V. R. S. Rao, A. K. Tiwari, K. S. Babu, P. V. Srinivas, A. Z. Ali and J. M. Rao, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 1659.
16. A. K. Tiwari, R. M. Kumbhare, S. B. Agawane, A. Z. Ali and K. V. Kumar, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 4130.
17. M. D. P. Risseuw, R. J. B. H. N. van den Berg, W. E. Donker-Koopman, G. A. van der Marel, J. M. F. G. Aerts, M. Overhand and H. S. Overkleeft, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 6600.
18. P. P. Reddy, A. K. Tiwari, R. R. Rao, K. Madhusudana, V. R. S. Rao, A. Z. Ali, K. S. Babu and J. M. Rao, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 2562.
19. R. R. Rao, A. K. Tiwari, P. P. Reddy, K. S. Babu, A. Z. Ali, K. Madhusudana and J. M. Rao, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **17**, 5170.
20. F. V. Singh, A. Parihar, S. Chaurasia, A. B. Singh, S. P. Singh, A. K. Tamrakar, A. K. Srivastava and A. Goel, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 2158.
21. S. S. Bisht, S. Fatima, A. K. Tamrakar, N. Rahuja, N. Jaiswal and A. K. Srivastava, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2009, **19**, 2699.
22. B. China Raju, A. K. Tiwari, J. A. Kumar, A. Z. Ali, S. B. Agawane, G. Saidachary and K. Madhusudana, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **18**, 358.
23. M. M. Si, J. S. Lou, C. X. Zhou, J. N. Shen, H. H. Wu, B. Yang, Q. J. He and H. S. Wu, *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 2010, **128**, 154.
24. J. A. Kumar, A. K. Tiwari, A. Z. Ali, K. Madhusudana, B. S. Reddy, S. Ramakrishna and B. China Raju, *J. Enz. Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **25**, 80.
25. H. Sakurai, H. Watanabe, H. Tamura, H. Yasui and R. Matsushita, *J. Takada, Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1998, **283**, 175.
26. K. H. Thompson, J. H. McNeill and C. Orvig, *Chem Rev.*, 1999, **99**, 2561.
27. D. Rehder, J. C. Pessoa, C. F. Geraldes, M. M. Castro, T. Kabanos, T. Kiss, B. Meier, G. Mírcera, L. Pettersson, M. Rangel, A. Salifoglou, I. Turel and D. Wang, *J. Biol. Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, **7**, 384.
28. H. Sakurai, *Chem. Rec.*, 2002, **2**, 237.
29. H. Sakurai, A. Tamura, J. Fugono, H. Yasui and T. Kiss, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **245**, 31.
30. H. Sakurai, H. Yasui and Y. Adachi, *Expert Opin. Invest. Drug.* 2003, **12**, 1189.
31. D. C. Crans, *Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2005, **77**, 1497.
32. A. Katoh, Y. Matsumura, Y. Yoshikawa, H. Yasui and H. Sakurai, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2009, **103**, 567.
33. H. Esbak, J. Nilsson, E. Nordlander, E. A. Enyedy, T. Kiss, Y. Yoshikawa, H. Sakurai and D. Rehder, *J. Argent. Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **97**, 51.
34. C. Orvig, K. H. Thompson, B. D. Loboiron, J. H. McNeill and V. G. Yuen, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2003, **96**, 14.
35. N. Durai and G. Saminathan, *J. Clin. Biochem Nutr*, 1997, **22**, 31.
36. U. Ashiq, R. Ara, M. M. Tahir, Z. T. Maqsood, K. M. Khan, S. N. Khan, H. Siddiqui and M. I. Choudhary, *Chemistry and Biodiversity*, 2008, **5**, 82.
37. U. Ashiq, R. A. Jamal, M. M. Tahir, Z. T. Maqsood, K. M. Khan, I. Omer and M. I. Choudhary, *J. Enzyme Inhib. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **8**, 1336.
38. D. F. Rohrbach, W. R. Heineman and E. Deutsch, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 2536.
39. A. H. Kianfar and S. Mohebbi, *J. Iran Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **4**, 215.
40. K. B. Pandeya and D. Khare, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **69**, 522.
41. C. R. Cornman, E. P. Zovinka and M. H. Meixner, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **34**, 5099.
42. J. M. Zhou, J. H. Zhou, Y. Meng and M. B. Chen, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, 2006, **2**, 157.
43. H. Park, K. Y. Hwang, Y. H. Kim, K. H. Oh, J. Y. Lee and K. Kim, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2008, **18**, 3711.
44. A. Horn (Jr.), C. A. L. Filgueiras, J. L. Wardell, M. H. Herbst, N. V. Vugman, P. S. Santos, J. G. S. Lopes and R. A. Howie, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 4240.
45. D. M. Murphy, I. A. Fallis, E. Carter, D. J. Willock, J. Landon, S. Van Doorslaer and E. Vinck, *Phys Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2009, **11**, 6757.

